

Studies on the Biginelli reaction : Synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-thiones via arylidene intermediate and one pot reaction

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Abstract : The series of 4-aryl-6-isopropyl-5-[N-(3-nitrophenyl)aminocarbonyl]-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-thiones **2a-l** were prepared via arylidene (route-1) intermediates by condensing 2-arylidene-4-methyl-N-(3-nitrophenyl)-3-oxopentanamide and thiourea in the presence of potassium bicarbonate. Then **2a-l** were prepared by single step (route-2) in the presence of conc. HCl catalyst, with better yield in short time compare to route-1. Some of these compounds showed potential antimicrobial activity.

Keywords : Biginelli reaction, arylidene, one pot reaction, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

The synthesis of functionalized 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-(1H)-thiones (Scheme 1) represents an excellent example of the utility of one-pot multiple component condensation reactions. Readily assembled as racemates by the Biginelli reaction, DHPMs display a range of useful pharmacological activity¹⁻³. The reaction has traditionally been catalyzed by strong mineral acids, but more recently has been performed using numerous milder Lewis acid and heteropoly acid catalysts. The use of multi component reactions (MCRs) to generate interesting and novel drug like scaffolds is replete in the recent chemical literature⁴. The demand for preparing libraries of compounds of diverse structures for screening in drug discovery is the driving force behind the development of new methodologies and structural motifs. In the area of calcium channel modulators, appropriately functionalized DHPMs occupy a place of prominence and more recently these have emerged as potent antihypertensive agents, α -adrenergic antagonists and mitotic kinesin inhibitors⁵. A number of improved variants of the classical Biginelli condensation employing new reagents, catalysts, methodologies and techniques have been reported⁶. The classical Biginelli synthesis is a one pot condensation using aceto *m*-chloroacetanilide, thiourea and aromatic aldehyde in ethanol⁷.

Results and discussion

When HCl was used (route-2) as a catalyst in the three-

component Biginelli reaction of β -dicarbonyl compound, aryl aldehyde, and thiourea in a ratio of 1 : 1 : 2, dihydropyrimidine of type **2a-l** were produced within a few hours in moderate to high yields of 71 to 86% (Scheme 1). Thereby, both electron-poor and electron-rich aromatic aldehydes proved to be reactive. DHPMs were prepared by route-1, which normally produce poor yields and long time duration compare to route-2. Yield and data are recorded in Table 1.

Antimicrobial screening :

The antimicrobial activity was carried out by using the cup-plate agar diffusion method⁸ by measuring the zone of inhibition in millimeter. All the compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against variety of bacterial strain such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and fungi *Aspergillus niger* using dimethyl sulfoxide as solvent at 40 μ g concentration. Standard drugs like amoxicillin, benzyl penicillin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin and griseofulvin were used for comparison purpose.

The screening data indicated that among dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-thione derivatives tested compounds **2b**, **2d**, **2h**, **2k** and **2l** showed greater degree of antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*. However, the compounds **2c**, **2e**, **2f**, **2g**, **2h** and **2k** showed greater degree of antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis*. The compounds **2a**, **2b**, **2e**, **2h**, **2i** and **2c**, **2d**, **2e**, **2f**, **2h**, **2j** showed greater degree of antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *P.*

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physical data of compounds 2a-l

Compd.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. (°C)	N (%)		Yield (%)	
				Calcd.	(Found)	Route-1	Route-2
2a	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	122	14.14	(14.12)	42	72
2b	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	168	13.14	(13.12)	55	86
2c	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₅ S	135	12.28	(12.19)	47	71
2d	4-(OH)-3-(OCH ₃)-C ₆ H ₃ -	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₅ S	239	12.66	(12.72)	47	75
2e	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	174	13.59	(13.57)	61	78
2f	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	178	13.59	(13.61)	51	73
2g	4-F-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ FN ₄ O ₃ S	244	13.52	(13.57)	62	83
2h	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	172	13.02	(12.97)	57	81
2i	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	>250	13.02	(13.08)	66	82
2j	3,4-(Cl) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₃ S	190	12.04	(12.07)	57	79
2k	3-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ BrN ₄ O ₃ S	142	11.78	(11.81)	56	82
2l	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅ S	170	15.87	(15.89)	64	76

aeruginosa respectively. The compounds **2a**, **2c**, **2e** and **2g** showed greater degree of antifungal activity against *A. niger*.

Experimental

The melting points were determined using capillary method and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR-8400 instrument in KBr pellets defined peaks (cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker spectrometer 400 MHz using TMS as an internal standard, chemical shift were measured in δ ppm. Mass spectrum was recorded on a Jeol D-300 spectrometer. The purity of compounds was checked by using TLC plate. All the synthesized compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis were carried out on a Carlo Erba 1108 analyzer.

General procedure for the preparation of 4-aryl-6-isopropyl-5-[N-(3-nitrophenyl)aminocarbonyl]-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-thiones by using route-1 (2a-1) :

Step-1 (1a-1) : Synthesis of 2-arylidene-4-methyl-N-(3-nitrophenyl)-3-oxo pentanamides :

To mixture of aryl aldehyde (0.01 mol) and 4-methyl-N-(3-nitrophenyl)-3-oxopentanamide 2.50 g (0.01 mol) in toluene, catalytic amount of morpholine and acetic acid were added and the mixture was heated at reflux temperature with continuous water removal by dean and stark for 22 h. After completion of the reaction, it was cooled at room temperature and the solid product was filtered. The product was washed with toluene and sodium meta bisulphite solution.

Step-2 (2a-1) : Synthesis of 4-aryl-6-isopropyl-5-[N-(3-nitrophenyl)aminocarbonyl]-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-thiones :

A mixture of 2-arylidene-4-methyl-N-(3-nitrophenyl)-3-oxopentanamide (0.01 mol) and thiourea 0.76 g (0.01 mol) was dissolved in DMSO. Potassium bicarbonate was added to the reaction mixture and the mixture was stirred at 45–55 °C for 20 h. The reaction mixture was cooled at room temperature. It was poured into a mixture of crushed ice, dilute HCl and toluene, stirred for 1 h then the water layer was separated and pH was adjusted to 9–10 using liq. NH₃. Solid material was filtered and washed with water and finally recrystallized from isopropyl alcohol.

General procedure for the preparation of 4-aryl-6-isopropyl-5-[N-(3-nitrophenyl)aminocarbonyl]-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-thiones by using route-2 (2a-1) :

A mixture of thiourea 1.5 g (0.02 mol), aryl aldehyde

(0.01 mol) and 4-methyl-N-(3-nitrophenyl)-3-oxopentanamide 2.50 g (0.01 mol) in 25 ml methanol containing 2–3 drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid was refluxed for 5 h. The solution was allowed to stand for 1 h at room temperature. The product was filtered and recrystallized from isopropyl alcohol.

The physical data of all synthesized compounds are recorded in Table 1.

Compounds **2a-1** have been characterized by ¹H NMR (in δ ppm), IR (KBr disc) cm⁻¹ and Mass *m/z* value. For 4-(2-chlorophenyl)-6-isopropyl-5-[N-(3-nitrophenyl)aminocarbonyl]-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-thione (**2i**) characterization data are found as under.

(**2i**), IR (KBr) : 3381 (NH, str.), 2980 (C–H, asym.), 2860 (C–H, sym.), 1680 (C=O, str.), 1207 (C=S, str.), 1491 (C–H, def.), 1531 (C=C), 3109 (Ar C–H), 1346 cm⁻¹ (NO₂, str.).

¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm : 1.49 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.76 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.89 (1H, m, CH), 5.55–5.56 (1H, d, chiral-H, *J* 4.16 Hz), 8.6 (1H, s, NH-CO), 8.78–8.79 (1H, d, NH near chiral center, *J* 4.36 Hz), 9.22 (1H, s, -NH near isopropyl).

2-Chloro aromatic ring : 7.11–7.13 (1H, doublet, Ar-H₆, *J* 5.64 Hz), 7.25–7.27 (2H, doublet, Ar-H₄ and 5, *J* 5.98 Hz), 7.36–7.38 (1H, doublet, Ar-H₃).

3-Nitro aromatic ring : 7.49–7.54 (1H, t, Ar-H₅), 7.93–7.95 (1H, d, Ar-H₆, *J* 8.08, 1.6 Hz), 8.12–8.15 (1H, d, Ar-H₄, *J* 8.12, 1.2 Hz), 8.59 (1H, s, Ar-H₂).

Mass spectrum *m/z* value : 430, 395, 387, 319, 308, 153, 122, 111, 77.

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